

Rearrangement of Heteroaromatic *N*-Oxides. A New Synthesis of Chloromethylquinoline

NEETA SINHA and R. SINHA*

Chemistry Department, T. N. B. Postgraduate College, Bhagalpur University, Bhagalpur-812 007

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A perusal of literature¹ shows no available methods for the introduction of a chlorine atom into one of the methyl groups of 2,4-dimethylquinoline. We now report a two-step synthesis of pure 2-chloromethyl-4-methylquinoline (**2**) from 2,4-dimethylquinoline. This is first converted into *N*-oxide (**1**) which on refluxing with phosphoryl chloride furnished **2**, free from isomers. Analytical data show that there is one chlorine atom in the molecule. The nmr signals for the 2- and 4-methyl groups appear as singlets at δ 2.70 and 2.64 respectively in the case of 2,4-dimethylquinoline². Further, ir spectrum reveals peaks at 860 and 740 cm^{-1} for an isolated hydrogen atom in the pyridine moiety and four adjacent hydrogen atoms in the benzene moiety³ respectively. Compound **1** on heating with acetic anhydride furnished 2-acetoxy-4-methylquinoline (**3**). The ester (**3**) on hydrolysis with hydrochloric acid and working up the reaction mixture furnished the free alcohol (**4**). Furukawa⁴ obtained **3** as liquid over a wide range of temperature suggesting the compound to be very impure. When **1** was heated with phosphorus trichloride, it was

smoothly deoxygenated to the parent base in nearly quantitative yield. Thus this is much a cleaner and better method for the reduction than the usual procedure of reduction with zinc and acetic acid.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Electronic spectra (EtOH) were recorded on Beckmann DK-2A spectrophotometer, ir spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer IR-20 infracord spectrophotometers and nmr spectra (CDCl_3) on a Varian A-60 spectrometer with TMS as an internal standard. All the compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

2-Chloromethyl-4-methylquinoline (2) : 2,4-Dimethylquinoline-*N*-oxide (**1**, 0.01 mol) was added cautiously during 0.25 h to boiling POCl_3 (20 g), then refluxed on a water-bath for 3 h and further heated at 120° for 1 h. The unreacted POCl_3 was neutralised with a saturated solution of NaHCO_3 and then filtered. The filtrate was extracted with chloroform, dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 , filtered and distilled under reduced pressure (140°/2 mm) to yield **2** which was crystallised from light petroleum (b.p. 40–60°) as white crystals (68%), m.p. 64°, R_f 0.62 (CHCl_3 and C_6H_6 , 1 : 1); λ_{max} (EtOH) 317 (ϵ 8275), 305 (7960) and 280 nm (7510); ν_{max} 3 020 (CH), 2 960 (CH_3), 1 592 (aromatic), 1 370 (CH_3), 850 (one isolated hydrogen atom) and

745 cm^{-1} (4 adjacent hydrogen atoms); δ 2.65 (3H, s, 4CH₃), 4.75 (2H, s, 2CH₂Cl) and 7.25–8.12 (5H, m, ArH).

2-Chloromethyl-4-methylquinoline picrate : To 2-chloromethyl-4-methylquinoline (0.25 g) dissolved in benzene (4 ml), a saturated solution of picric acid in benzene was added. The separated solid was recrystallised from ethanol as yellow crystals, m.p. 187–88° (Found : N, 13.64 C₁₇H₁₃N₄O₆Cl requires : N, 13.84%).

2-Acetoxy-4-methylquinoline (3) : The *N*-oxide (1; 0.01 mol) was added to gently boiling acetic anhydride (15 ml) in 0.25 h. The mixture was heated on a water-bath for 3 h. The excess of acetic anhydride was then removed under reduced pressure and the remaining solution was distilled to yield a viscous oil, b.p. 150–52°/3 mm (lit. 110–45°/2 mm). The resulting yellow solid was crystallised from light petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) as white needles (58%), m.p. 61.5°; R_f 0.75 (C₆H₆ and CH₃OH, 95 : 5); λ_{max} (EtOH) 317, 304, 289 and 280 nm; ν_{max} 3060 (CH), 2925 (CH₃), 1738 (C=O ester), 1597 (aromatic), 1376 (CH₃), 860 (one isolated H atom) and 755 cm^{-1} (4 adjacent H atoms); δ 2.15 (3H, s, COCH₃), 2.65 (3H, s, CH₃), 5.4 (2H, s, CH₂) and 7.2–8.1 (5H, m, ArH).

2-Hydroxymethyl-4-methylquinoline (4) : **3** (0.01 mol) was refluxed with 10% HCl (35 ml) for 8 h, then concentrated in a stream of air and the remaining acid was neutralised with a strong solution of K₂CO₃ and filtered. The filtrate was extracted with ether (2 × 30 ml), dried over Na₂SO₄ and ether recovered to give a solid which was crystallised from benzene as yellow needles (62%), m.p. 257° (lit⁶. m.p.

74–75°). Tlc showed one component : R_f 0.44 (C₆H₆ and MeOH, 2 : 1); λ_{max} (EtOH) 317 (ϵ 8150), 304 (6675), 290 (7585) and 277 nm (8645); ν_{max} 3420 (OH), 2940 (CH₃), 1597 (aromatic), 1390 (CH₃), 860 (one isolated H atom) and 755 cm^{-1} (four adjacent H atoms); δ 2.66 (3H, s, CH₃ at 4-position), 4.95 (2H, s, CH₂ at 2-position) and 7.2–8.2 (5H, m, ArH).

De-oxygenation of 2,4-dimethylquinoline-N-oxide (1) : 2,4-Dimethylquinoline-*N*-oxide (1; 0.02 mol) was added portionwise to gently boiling PCl₃ (10 g). The mixture was refluxed for 3 h, then cooled, neutralised with NaHCO₃ solution, filtered and the filtrate was extracted with chloroform and dried over Na₂SO₄. Chloroform was then recovered and the remaining liquid was distilled to get a colourless liquid (96%), b.p. 110°/5 mm; its picrate did not show any depression with the picrate of an authentic sample.

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